

Template - Processing analysis

Template to process all surfaces acquired with the LSM with the 50x/0.75 and 50x/0.95 objectives.

Processing

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x_natural_d_Topo		
Created on:	4/15/2021 12:01:50 PM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	31.80	µm	
Size:	65532	digits	
Spacing:	0.4852	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x...filtered (λ s 2.500 μm)		
File path:	D:\...\Kremasti4_LSM_50x_natural_d_Topo.sur		
Created on:	4/15/2021 12:01:50 PM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	0.000	μm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	-255.5	μm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	16.09	μm	
Min:	-7.055	μm	
Max:	9.032	μm	
Size:	331541	digits	
Spacing:	0.04852	nm	
NM-points ratio:	11.07 % (996050 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x_na...in non-measured points		
Created on:	4/15/2021 12:01:50 PM		
Studiable type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	16.09	μm	
Size:	331541	digits	
Spacing:	0.04852	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Analyses

8. ISO 25178-2 parameters on surface #7

ISO 25178 - Primary surface			
<i>F: [Workflow] Form removed (LS-poly 3)</i>			
<i>S-filter (λs): [Workflow] S-filtered (λs 2.500 μm)</i>			
Height parameters			
Sq	2.241	μm	
Ssk	-0.04897		
Sku	3.436		
Sp	9.023	μm	
Sv	7.064	μm	
Sz	16.09	μm	
Sa	1.765	μm	
Functional parameters			
Smr	0.2066	%	
Smc	2.873	μm	
Sxp	4.647	μm	
Spatial parameters			
Sal	30.57	μm	
Str	0.6142		
Std	25.25	°	
Hybrid parameters			
Sdq	0.4030		
Sdr	6.729	%	
Functional parameters (Volume)			
Vm	0.09941	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vv	2.972	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vmp	0.09941	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vmc	1.844	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vvc	2.680	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vvv	0.2923	μm ³ /μm ²	

Analyses:

ISO 25178	8.
Furrow	9.
Texture direction	10.
Texture isotropy	11.
SSFA	12.

9. Furrow analysis on surface #7

All furrows are shown.

Parameters	Value	Unit
Maximum depth of furrows	6.760	µm
Mean depth of furrows	1.904	µm
Mean density of furrows	3480	cm/cm2

10. Texture direction on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
First direction	0.01225	°
Second direction	26.48	°
Third direction	89.99	°

11. Texture isotropy on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
Texture isotropy	90.32	%

12. SSFA on surface #7

